

On the Burnup of Fuel Followed Control Rods in TRIGA Reactors

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ABSTRACT

The impact of three-dimensional fuel burnup accumulation in fuel-followed control rods (FFCRs) at the JSI TRIGA reactor is evaluated computationally and experimentally using 35 years of integral and differential worth measurements. Due to high experimental uncertainties, the measurement record does not reveal clear systematic trends that could be attributed to accumulated burnup effects. To complement the data, a computational analysis was performed assuming the average control-rod positions used during steady-state operation. The results indicate that two FFCRs that usually remain inserted during operation accumulate asymmetric burnup. The corresponding changes in integral and differential worth were quantified by comparing models with and without burnup. When burnup is included, the integral and differential worth increase by approximately 100 pcm and 0.3 pcm/step, respectively. Including burnup also reduces the discrepancy between measured integral and differential worth by about 25 %. A clear asymmetric change in differential worth is observed: 0.3 pcm/step when the rod is more withdrawn and 0.1 pcm/step when it is nearly fully inserted. This behavior demonstrates that asymmetric burnup accumulation has a direct, measurable effect on FFCR worth. These findings are relevant for all TRIGA research reactors as well as future small modular reactor (SMR) and microreactor designs, where compact cores and FFCR configurations can lead to non-uniform burnup patterns that produce noticeable reactivity-worth changes.

Keywords: TRIGA reactor, fuel follower control rods, burnup, integral worth, differential worth

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in nuclear technology have driven development toward increasingly small systems, notably small modular reactors (SMRs) (typically <300 MWe) [1] and microreactors (typically <20 MWe) [2]. These concepts favor compact core lattices, longer refueling intervals, and load-following capability. In this operating regime, reactivity control is crucial: the system must provide a wide dynamic range, sufficient shutdown margin, and stable controllability throughout the fuel cycle. Common solutions include control drums surrounding the core and conventional control rods (CRs) equipped with a fuelled follower (FFCRs - Fuel-followed control rods) in which a neutron absorber section is followed by a fuel section that enters the core as the rod is withdrawn [3]. This configuration increases control-rod worth while enabling criticality in a smaller core.

FFCRs have been and continue to be used in TRIGA (Training, Research, Isotope, General Atomics) reactors, which are known as the most widely used research reactors in the world (a total of 66 TRIGA reactors have been installed). Although TRIGA reactors have been in operation since the 1960s, new knowledge relevant to modern reactor designs can still be obtained. In addition to the benefits of FFCRs (compactness and higher reactivity worth), a higher level of complexity arises because the FFCR reactivity worth is no longer solely a function of the absorber, but also depends on the fuel in the follower, as well as the current isotopic composition or burnup level of the fuel. This was studied for JRR-3 (Japan

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Research Reactor - 3), where the results show that control rod worth is significantly affected by the relationship between fuel follower (FF) burnup and the local burnups around the control rods [4]. Such problems become even more complex when the actual operation of TRIGA reactors is studied.

In the TRIGA research reactor at the "Jožef Stefan Institute" (JSI), Slovenia, operation at full power is usually performed with two control rods (equipped with fuelled followers) inserted halfway and one completely extracted [5]. This means that, for two FFCRs, on average only half of the fuelled follower is inserted into the active part of the reactor core, resulting in an asymmetrical axial distribution of fuelled follower burnup. The effect of such burnup profiles in the fuel of FFCRs on integral and differential control rod worths has not yet been studied. Recent efforts to record the operational history and calculate the detailed 3D fuel burnup distribution [6] make the JSI TRIGA an ideal scenario to test these effects. This paper presents the effects of asymmetrical axial burnup accumulation in the fuelled follower over a period of more than 30 years on the integral and differential worths of the three FFCRs of the JSI TRIGA reactor.

The first section of the paper introduces the JSI TRIGA reactor with its FFCRs and the calculated asymmetrical burnup profile. The second section presents the analysis of 30 years of control rod worth data to determine whether any long-term effects are observed. The final sections present the computational analysis of fuelled follower burnup on the integral and differential static reactivity worths of the FFCRs.

2. FFCR'S AT JSI TRIGA RESEARCH REACTOR

The JSI TRIGA reached first criticality on 31 May 1966 and has been highly utilized since then [5] for research, education and training, industrial applications, and isotope production (prior to 1991). In 1991, a major reconstruction of the reactor was carried out, replacing key components such as the three control rods – SAFE, REGU, and SHIM – each equipped with a fuel follower (FFCRs), and introducing a fourth transient control rod (without a fuel follower), named TRAN, enabling pulse mode operation [7]. Schematics of the control rods used before and after the reconstruction are shown in Figure 1. The FFCR has a 38.6 cm B_4C absorber at the top, followed by 38.1 cm of fuel with a zirconium rod in the centre. The fuel type used in the FFCRs and all other fuel elements is a 12.0 wt.% of 19.9 % enriched uranium in a U-Zr-H mixture.

Figure 1. Top: Schematic view of JSI TRIGA Control rods equipped with a Fuel Follower (top). Bottom: Schematic of the old control rods, used before 1991.

In recent years, extensive burnup analysis of the JSI TRIGA fuel has been conducted by analyzing the entire operational history. Individual operation was analysed to obtain the released energy and fuel loading patterns [6]. The methodology used involved simulating all the released energy as a single operation at full reactor power of 250 kW, updating the computational model each time the core configuration changed. This approach was verified using excess reactivity measurements obtained from the operational analysis [8]. However, for the positions of the FFCRs, the all rods out (ARO) position was assumed throughout the calculations. As the burnup axial profile of the FFCRs depends on the position of the control rods, the entire burnup simulation was repeated with the control rods set to their most probable position.

2.1. Determination of FFCR burnups

During steady-state operation of the JSI TRIGA reactor at full power (250 kW), the average positions of the control rods are as follows: TRAN - Up, SAFE - Up, REGU - 40 % inserted, and SHIM - 40 % inserted. By inserting the regulating (REGU) and compensating (SHIM) control rods to the same levels, reactor operators reduce the neutron flux tilt caused by control rod insertion [9]. The average CR position was determined by analysing one full-power operation each year since 1991 (a total of 34 operations). In most operations, the insertion heights of both REGU and SHIM control rods were the same, varying only due to differences in core configurations (inserting or swapping fuel elements). However, some operations were long enough for xenon to build up and have a noticeable effect on core reactivity. In such cases, compensation was performed with only one rod. Both of these effects, along with some operations at different control rod positions, can result in large uncertainties in CR position. Based on the operational analysis, a large conservative CR axial position uncertainty of 5 cm (corresponding to approximately 13 % of the total length) was assumed in the burnup simulations. This uncertainty can be reduced in the future by analysing all control rod positions in the operational history, as well as by dividing burnup simulations for each individual operation, although both approaches are computationally extremely demanding. Figure 2 graphically presents the average insertion of REGU and SHIM rods, together with the calculated burnup distribution of fuel in all FFCRs. Burnup calculations were performed using the Serpent-2 Monte Carlo code, based on the methodology presented in [6].

Figure 2. Average position of FFCR's during steady state JSI TRIGA operation at 250 kW. The safety FFCR (SAFE) is shown separately. In addition axial profile of the accumulated burnup from 1991 to 2025 is shown.

The results clearly indicate a difference in axial burnup distribution in the fuel follower of CRs between the SAFE and REGU/SHIM types, as the former is fully inserted during operation, while the latter two are inserted by approximately 40 %. The axial profile of the SAFE control rod is similar to the burnup of standard fuel elements [6]; however, the burnup profile of SAFE and SHIM fuelled follower is shown to be highly asymmetrical. The effect of this asymmetry on control rod integral and differential worths is discussed in the following chapters.

3. ANALYSIS OF FFCR WORTH MEASUREMENTS 1991-2025

As an initial step in researching the burnup effects of fuel-followed control rods (FFCRs), all available measurements of FFCR worths throughout the history of the JSI TRIGA were analysed. Measurements are typically performed annually; however, this can vary depending on changes in the core loading pattern and reactor operation. In total, 31 measurements for each SHIM, REGU, and SAFE FFCR were analysed. The primary aim was to identify a trend over time that would indicate a consistent change in both integral and differential worth, potentially linked to the accumulation of burnup in the FFCR. A further objective was to identify any possible differences between the SAFE and REGU/SHIM FFCRs, which could indicate a secondary effect due to previously demonstrated asymmetrical burnup build-up. The results of the changes in integral and differential FFCR worths over time are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3. Left: FFCR integral worth through JSI TRIGA history with linear trend. Right: SAFE FFCR differential worth through the JSI TRIGA history.

The analysis of differential worth changes throughout the JSI TRIGA history shows a somewhat different picture. The variability over the years is also high (2–3 pcm per step in the most worth section of the FFCR). However, there is a consistent trend across all FFCRs: the differential worth in recent years is lower than in the first ten years of operation with FFCRs. This effect cannot be directly attributed to burnup accumulation, as many core parameters have changed over the years, including the procedure for measuring control rod worth [10] and the core loading pattern, which has become less compact in recent years [6]. To evaluate the burnup effect experimentally, consistency would be required throughout the history, both in loading pattern and measurement methods. Additionally, computational analysis of the effects of other changes on control rod worth would be necessary to isolate the impact of burnup accumulation. It can be concluded that, based on the available measurements of FFCR worth at the JSI TRIGA reactor, the effect of FF burnup accumulation cannot be observed, and computational analysis is required, as presented in the next Section 4.

By analysing the changes in the integral value of all FFCRs throughout history, it can be seen that the integral value of all rods varies significantly (up to 1000 pcm), which corresponds to the uncertainty in CR worth measurements and changes in the core loading pattern. It can be observed that in recent years, the measurements of integral worth have become more consistent. No direct trends in changes over time can be identified, indicating that if a burnup effect exists, it is within the uncertainty of the measured FFCR worths. However, it should be noted that since 1991, both the accuracy and reproducibility of CR worths have increased, and data indicating burnup changes may become available in the future.

The analysis of differential worth changes throughout the JSI TRIGA history shows a bit different pic-

Figure 4. REGU (left) and SHIM (right) FFCR differential worth through the JSI TRIGA history.

ture. The variability through the years is high as well (2-3 pcm per step in the most worth section of the FFCR), although, there is a consistent trend among all FFCRs that differential worth in recent years is smaller than in the first 10 years of operation with FFCRs. This effect cannot be directly connected to burnup accumulation, as the many core parameters changed throughout the years, the procedure how CR worth is measured [10], core loading pattern became less compact in recent years [6], etc. In order to evaluate the burnup effect experimentally, consistency would be needed throughout the history (both in loading pattern and method of measurements). In addition, computational analysis into effect other changes have on CR worth would have to be performed, to isolate the burnup accumulation effects. It can be concluded that from the available measurements of FFCR worth at JSI TRIGA reactor, burnup accumulation effect of the FF cannot be observed and computational analysis is needed, which is presented in the next Section 4.

4. CALCULATED BURNUP EFFECTS ON FFCR WORTH

The effects of burnup accumulation in the fuel of the Fuel Followed Control Rods (FFCRs) of the JSI TRIGA reactor were studied using the Serpent-2 Monte Carlo code [11] with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library [12]. Two geometrical models of the current JSI TRIGA loading pattern were created: one with all fuel assumed fresh, and one with all fuel burned (including both standard fuel elements and FFCRs), as calculated and presented in Section 2. For each model, the reactivity effects of SAFE, REGU, and SHIM FFCR insertion were calculated by eigenvalue Monte Carlo (MC) simulation at different levels of individual control rod insertion. The simulation discretisation was set to 10 steps (0.54 cm), resulting in 70 MC simulations per control rod and 420 in total (8 hours per simulation¹). MC eigenvalue simulation parameters were 10^6 neutrons per cycle, 2000 active cycles, and 40 cycles for source convergence. This resulted in an uncertainty of 3 pcm in the calculated k_{eff} .

As the steady-state for each rod insertion level was calculated, the static reactivity of the FFCR was determined, corresponding to control rod worth measurements performed using the rod swap method. However, at the JSI TRIGA reactor, the rod insertion method [10] is used for control rod worth measurements, which measures the dynamic reactivity and requires time-dependent simulations [13]. The results presented in this paper therefore show the burnup effects on static reactivity changes in terms of both integral and differential FFCR worths, making a direct comparison with absolute FFCR worth measurements biased and thus beyond the scope of this paper.

¹On one node of JSI's cluster – 2 × 28 cores Intel Xeon Gold 6238R

4.1. Changes of FFCR integral worth due to fuel burnup

As a first step in the computational analysis, integral FFCR worths were calculated for both fresh and burned fuel. The results are presented in Figure 5. It can be observed that for all three FFCRs, the integral worth increases when burnup is taken into account. The Safety FFCR (SAFE) shows the smallest integral worth difference of $50 \text{ pcm} \pm 5 \text{ pcm}$, while the REGU and SHIM rods (not fully extracted during operation) exhibit a higher and consistent integral worth increase of $102 \text{ pcm} \pm 5 \text{ pcm}$, indicating a noticeable difference between the rods.

Figure 5. Integral control-rod worth for fuel-followed control rods (FFCRs). **Left:** Integral worth with burned fuel (points with 1σ error bars). **Right:** Integral worth difference (Burned – Fresh) with a shaded 1σ statistical uncertainty band. The gray vertical band indicates FFCR fully in (positions 180–200), and the thick black line marks FFCR fully out at position 900.

For all FFCRs, the calculated integral worth underestimates the measurements by 250 pcm, which is consistent with the findings in [13], where a comparison between static and dynamic reactivity was studied. Inclusion of fuel burnup reduces the discrepancy between the measurements and calculations. As the REGU and SHIM rods are in different positions in the core compared to the SAFE control rod, it cannot be concluded that asymmetrical burnup accumulation in the fuel of FFCRs is responsible for the difference. Differential worth must be studied.

4.2. Changes of FFCR differential worth due to fuel burnup

To analyse the possible effect of asymmetrical burnup accumulation in the fuel of the FFCRs, the differential worth of FFCRs was studied for both fresh and burned fuel cases. The differential worth was calculated as the derivative of the integral worth, using a derivative window of 5 points to minimise the effects of statistical uncertainty. The results are presented in Figure 6. It can be immediately observed that the statistical noise in the calculated differential worths is higher; however, statistically relevant effects are still evident. The computed differential worth, compared to the measurements, is underestimated by up to $1 \frac{\text{pcm}}{\text{step}}$, consistent with reports in [13]. Analysing the change in differential worth due to fuel burnup, an increase in differential worth for all three rods is observed, with a maximum of $0.3 \frac{\text{pcm}}{\text{step}}$. However, for REGU and SHIM FFCRs, an asymmetrical increase is observed, being larger when the FFCR is more extracted (between 0.2 and $0.3 \frac{\text{pcm}}{\text{step}}$) and reducing to $0 \frac{\text{pcm}}{\text{step}}$ when the FFCR is almost fully inserted. This aligns with the asymmetry of the accumulated burnup, as the bottom part of the

fuel in the FFCR, which is in the core when the rod is extracted, is more reactive due to lower burnup accumulation. A clear conclusion can be drawn that asymmetrical burnup accumulation in the fuel of FFCRs has an observable effect on the differential worth of the control rod.

Figure 6. Differential worth with burned fuel and its change relative to fresh. **Left:** Differential worth for burned fuel (with shaded 1 σ statistical uncertainty band). **Right:** Absolute change in differential worth (Burned – Fresh) with a 1 σ band.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fuel burnup effects for fuel follower control rods (FFCRs) were analysed both computationally and experimentally. Analysis of all control rod worth measurements at the JSI TRIGA reactor since 1991 showed no clear trends that would indicate that burnup accumulation affects either integral or differential control rod worths. The uncertainty in the measured values was too large for such effects to be noticeable. Computationally, burnup effects were studied by assuming an average FFCR position during steady-state operation at 250 kW, representing the maximum possible asymmetry in a TRIGA research reactor, as varying the positions of control rods over the years would distribute the burnup more evenly and reduce the asymmetry. This may be one explanation why it was not possible to obtain concrete conclusions from comparison with the measurements.

Analysing the calculated changes in integral and differential FFCR worth due to fuel burnup accumulation showed a clear increase in both integral and differential worths with burnup. From this, we can conclude that burnup must be included in future computational analyses. Furthermore, the analysis of burnup-induced changes in differential FFCR worths showed an asymmetrical increase in the axial direction, clearly indicating that asymmetrical burnup accumulation in the fuel of the FFCR has an effect. This conclusion is highly important for the SMR and microreactor designs, as it demonstrates that asymmetrical burnup accumulation could have a noticeable effect in compact systems equipped with FFCRs.

To analyse the observed effects in greater detail, we propose to further examine the reactor logbooks in the future to obtain information on control rod (CR) positions changes during each reactor operation. However, this would require simulating each individual operation from 1991 to 2025 (approximately 15,000 cases), which is currently computationally impossible with Monte Carlo burnup codes. Nevertheless, it can be calculated using other methodologies, such as the RAPID code system [14], equipped with control rod and burnup [15] methodologies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B.-J. Kim, Y. Bae, and P. Kim. "Decades of development: A bibliometric analysis of small modular reactor research." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **volume 57**(12), p. 103800 (2025).
- [2] T. G. Lane and S. T. Revankar. "Advances in technology, design and deployment of microreactors—a review." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 178**, p. 105520 (2025).
- [3] N. A. Kato Hidemasa and T. Akinobu. "Control rod with fuel follower, its driving mechanism and control method, as well as nuclear power plant and reactor operation method." (1992).
- [4] T. Hosoya, T. Kato, and Y. Murayama. "Investigation of JRR-3 control rod worth changed with burn-up of follower fuel elements." (2008).
- [5] L. Snoj et al. "A half-century of nuclear research, education and training: Story of the JSI TRIGA reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 214**, p. 111122 (2025).
- [6] A. Pungerčič, D. Čalič, and L. Snoj. "Computational burnup analysis of the TRIGA Mark II research reactor fuel." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 130**, p. 103536 (2020).
- [7] I. Švajger, D. Čalič, A. Pungerčič, A. Trkov, and L. Snoj. "Evaluation of reactor pulse experiments." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **volume 56**(4), pp. 1165–1203 (2024).
- [8] A. Pungerčič, A. Haghghat, and L. Snoj. "JSI TRIGA fuel rod reactivity worth experiments for validation of Serpent-2 and RAPID fuel burnup calculations." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **volume 56**(8), pp. 3405–3424 (2024).
- [9] T. Kaiba, G. Žerovnik, A. Jazbec, Žiga Štancar, L. Barbot, D. Fourmentel, and L. Snoj. "Validation of neutron flux redistribution factors in JSI TRIGA reactor due to control rod movements." *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, **volume 104**, pp. 34–42 (2015).
- [10] V. Merljak, M. Kromar, and A. Trkov. "Rod insertion method analysis—A methodology update and comparison to boron dilution method." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 113**, pp. 96–104 (2018).
- [11] J. Leppänen et al. "The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 142–150 (2015).
- [12] D. Brown et al. "ENDF/B-VIII.0: The 8th Major Release of the Nuclear Reaction Data Library with CIELO-project Cross Sections, New Standards and Thermal Scattering Data." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 148**, pp. 1–142 (2018).
- [13] V. Merljak et al. "Control Rod Insertion Method Analysis—Dynamic vs. Static Reactivity." *PHYSOR 2016: Unifying Theory and Experiments in the 21st Century*, pp. 1–5 (2016).
- [14] W. J. Walters, N. J. Roskoff, and A. Haghghat. "The RAPID fission matrix approach to reactor core criticality calculations." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 192**(1), pp. 21–39 (2018).
- [15] A. Pungerčič, V. Mascolino, A. Haghghat, and L. Snoj. "Verification of a novel fuel burnup algorithm in the RAPID code system based on Serpent-2 simulation of the TRIGA Mark II research reactor." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **volume 55**(10), pp. 3732–3753 (2023).